

Expression of TOM1-c006

Protein sequence:

MHHHHHSSMSPILGYWKIKGLVQPTRLLEYLEEKYEEHLYERDEGDKWRNKKFELGLEFPNLPYYIDGDVKLTQS
MAIIRYIADKHNMLGGCPKERAEL*/SMLEGAVLDIRYGVSRVIAYSKDFETLKVDFLSKLPEMLKMFEDRLCHKTYLN
GDHVTHPDFMLYDALDVVLYMDPMCLDAFPKLVCFKKRIEAIQIDKYLKSSKYIAWPLQGWQATFGGGDHPPKS
SSGVDLGTENLYFQSMRFRERFRTGQTTKAPSEAEPAADLIDMGPDPAATGNLSSQLAGMNLGSSSVRAGLQSLEA
SGRLEDE

*/ denotes tev cleavage site after His tag and GST tag.

Expression:

Set up overnight from glycerol stock in 100ml Kan+ LB media.

Incubate while shaking at 37c overnight

Innoculate 6 x 1L of LB with 12ml of overnight and grow while shaking at 160rpm for 3 hours until OD = 1.5 (a little high but I missed my window of opportunity).

Induce with 0.4mM IPTG

Reduce temperature to 18C and grow overnight

Harvest next morning at 5000rpm for 15 minutes.

Resuspend cells in 20ml binding buffer and freeze at -20C.